

Carbon-13 Nmr Substituent Shifts for the Substitution of 2-Isloxazoline in Butane

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Manuscript received 10 July 1992, accepted 12 November 1992

Isloxazolines have become versatile tools for synthesising β -hydroxyketones, γ -aminoalcohols, β -hydroxynitriles etc through their ability to undergo reductive cleavage with various reducing agents¹. Several biologically active compounds have been synthesised by employing the isloxazoline-reduction strategy². Detailed analysis of the mechanism of nitrile oxide cycloaddition has been done by several authors³. Though isloxazolines have found immense use as vehicles in organic synthesis, there are no reports on the carbon-13 nmr characteristics of these heterocycles. We had earlier determined methyl substituent parameters for C-5 methyl substitution in isloxazolines⁴ and in the present communication we report the substituent shifts of isloxazolines for substitution in butane. Substituent shifts of alkyl, phenyl, amino, halogeno, cyano, alkoxy, carboxy and sulphonyloxy groups for substitution in linear alkyl chains are available in the literature⁵.

Results and Discussion

The isloxazolines (1a–e and 2a–e) may be regarded as derivatives of butane and dimethyl sulphide, respectively. The chemical shifts for butane and 2-isloxazoline substituted butane, i.e. the isloxazolines 1a–e are compared and differential chemical shifts of the α , β , γ and δ carbons are collected in Table 1. From the data, it is seen that the α , β , γ and δ effects exerted by the 2-isloxazoline are 21.84, 2.72, –2.52 and 0.92 ppm, respectively. In a similar manner the substituent increments for substitution of 2-isloxazoline in dimethyl sulphide are derived from the chemical shifts values of 5-[(methylthio)methyl]isloxazolines (2a–e), relative to those of dimethyl sulphide. The differential chemical shifts observed in 2-isloxazoline substituted dimethyl sulphide show that the α -carbons are shifted downfield to about 18.80 ppm while the γ -carbons are shifted upfield to 3.04 ppm.

The carbon-13 nmr substituent increments for various groups (for substitution in linear alkanes) available in the literature are compared to the

shifts observed for substitution with 2-isloxazolines. The differential chemical shifts for various groups for substitution in butane are shown in Table 2.

TABLE 1—DIFFERENTIAL CHEMICAL SHIFTS OF THE BUTANE CARBONS SUBSTITUTED BY 2-ISLOXAZOLINE*

Isloxazo- line	R	Differential chemical shifts (ppm)			
		α	β	γ	δ
1a	CH ₃	22.02 (18.80)	2.80	-2.40 (-3.00)	0.92
1b	CH ₃ CH ₂	21.04 (18.80)	2.80	-2.40 (-3.12)	0.92
1c	C ₆ H ₅	22.12 (18.94)	2.78	-2.38 (-3.00)	1.00
1d	4-ClC ₆ H ₄	22.06 (18.70)	2.70	-2.40 (-3.06)	0.92
1e	3-NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄	21.98 (18.70)	2.54	-2.48 (-3.00)	0.98

*Value in parenthesis is for substitution in dimethyl sulphide system.

TABLE 2—SUBSTITUENT INCREMENTS FOR VARIOUS GROUPS UPON SUBSTITUTION IN LINEAR ALKANES

Group	Substituent increment (ppm)		
	α	β	γ
COOCH ₃ ^a	22.50	2.50	-3.00
CONH ₂ ^a	22.00	2.50	-3.00
COOH ^a	20.00	2.00	-3.00
C ₆ H ₅ ^a	23.00	9.00	-3.00
2-Isloxazoline	21.84	2.72	-2.41

^aData taken from Ref. 5.

The α -effects caused by 2-isloxazoline is very similar to those caused by COOCH₃, CONH₂, COOH and phenyl groups. However, the phenyl group deviates from these groups in causing an abnormally high β -effect (9 ppm downfield). The upfield shift observed in the case of substitution with 2-isloxazoline, on the γ -carbons is lesser in magnitude than those in the case of substitution with other groups.

The similarity in the shifts caused by 2-isloxazoline and certain other groups can be explained on the basis of the presence of electronegative oxygen atom β to the substitution site. The isloxazoline exerts an isotropic effect on the butane carbons by way of possessing β -C—C bond and γ π bond. Thus the isloxazoline ring causes a similar effect on the chemical shifts of the butane carbons analogous to those caused by COOH, CONH₂, COOCH₃ and phenyl groups.